

**Evaluating the Effectiveness of SMS Service of the
Department for Registration of Persons as an
M- Government Service**

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Master of Science in Development Communication and Extension

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Postgraduate Institute of Agriculture

University of Peradeniya

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DECLARATION

I do hereby declare that the work reported in this directed study was exclusively carried out by me under the supervision of Dr. U.I. Dissanayake. It describes the results of my own independent research except where due reference has been made in the text. No part of this dissertation has been submitted earlier or concurrently for the same or any other degree.

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ABSTRACT

The Department for Registration of Persons (DRP) started an SMS alert system as an m-governance service to aware clients on the completion of the one-day service. This service enabled clients to know the exact time to come and collect the NIC, and it helps the DRP to control the number of clients remaining in the office premises. This study aimed to evaluate the user acceptance of the m-governance service introduced by the DRP. The problems faced by the clients when obtaining the m-government service were also explored. Primary data were collected from 150 clients those who came for the one-day service of the DRP during the month of August 2022. Respondents were selected using stratified random sampling, and telephone interviews were conducted on the same day after they have collected the IDs. A five-point Likert- scale questionnaire was used to measure user satisfaction. According to the findings, user's age, gender, living area, awareness, English language skill, education level, ability to use technology, and perception on ease of use affected the usage and satisfaction of the SMS service. The results of the Spearman's Correlation test showed that the use of SMS service of DRP has statistically significant relationship with user satisfaction ($r=0.636$, $p=0.000$) and SMS usage ($r=0.472$, $p=0.000$). However, the SMS service is provided in only English, lack of awareness of SMS service, lack of trust of citizens in m-governance and e-governance services, and low technical skills of users were the main problems of the current system. Therefore, providing the message in trilingual to avoid language barriers and sending at least three SMS alerts to applicants were recommended to prevent problems with the SMS service of DRP.

Keyword m-government services, Department for Registration of Persons, Ease of Use, Usefulness, SMS, User satisfaction

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DRP	- Department for Registration of Persons
ICTA	- Information and Communication Technology Agency
ICT	- Information and Communication Technology
TRC	- Telecommunication Regulatory Commission
SMS	- Short Message Service
TAM	- Technology Acceptance Model
E- Government	- Electronic - government
M- Government	- Mobile - government
M- Extension	- Mobile - extension
EOU	- Ease Of Use
PENJ	- Perceived Enjoyment
PEU	- Perceived Ease of Use
PMV	- perceived monetary value
PU	- Perceived Usefulness
SI	- Social Influence
ATA	- Attitudes toward Acceptance

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. General Overview

Developing countries are currently dealing with technology and implementing changes in the public sector. It has been on the main agendas of international organizations since the 1980s' (Adhikari and Kuruppu, 2013). Accordingly, the ICT policy of Sri Lanka has been heavily contributed by local and international institutions, which aims to enhance quality and provide a sustainable start for a knowledge society. The contribution of information and communication technology is essential to the success of the public sector, not only in the private sector today (Dissanayake, 2011). To create active development of public sector services should use technical tools that the general public can easily use. Nowadays, as every person uses a mobile phone, it can be introduced as a suitable way to provide technology in service delivery.

The urban and rural public uses mobile phones as fast and straightforward devices. It can be introduced as the most popular ICT tool today, because of its' easy access, portability, small size, and high-cost effectiveness. That is why the number of subscribers has increased to 32.53 in Sri Lanka (TRCSL, 2019). Accordingly, the provision of e-government services by the government to the public can be widely seen, and ICT services are also taking priority today (Samansiri and Wanigasundera, 2014). Mobile Government (m-Government) is the next inevitable direction in the evolution of e-Government. It was created to enable people to get the government's help and provide new government functions and services to the public (Amailef, 2008). SMS technology under mobile technology is the possible way to deliver warning notifications and emergency alert information or government notices (Michael, 2007). Many government agencies in Sri Lanka are currently using the SMS service to provide information to the public under m- governance. The Department for Registration of Persons has also introduced this SMS service.

1.1.1. E-Governance

The provision of government service uses information and communication technology (ICTs) through the integration of government-to-citizen (G2C), government-to-business (G2B), and government-to-government (G2G). It is known as electronic governance (e-governance) (Susanto, and Goodwin, 2010). Citizens can access convenient, efficient, and transparent services by providing public services through e-governance, with easy interaction within the overall governance framework. As the concept of universal villages has evolved with globalization, electronic governance is a debated concept today. E-governance means using ICTs as servants to the master of good governance. Just as the advancement of information technology improves public Service, so does the development of public attitudes that lead to the rise of information technology (Heeks, 2001). Although there are no boundaries in e-Governance, it can enable efficient services for a country or its citizens. Therefore, the significant beneficiaries of e-Governance are primarily citizens, businesses, and other interest groups or the government itself (Garson, 2006).

There is a positive correlation between the advancement of information technology and the promotion of public Service. (Lallana, 2004). Today, the public sector is trying to develop in the form of the private sector and provide public services, at the forefront of which is the advancement of information technology. In terms of ICT applications, it has recently started recognizing the potential of digital initiatives in their responsiveness to the changing needs of citizens, efficiently using limited public resources, and, most importantly, encouraging more just and inclusive governance or participatory democracy (Tapscott, and Caston, 1992). Telecommunication systems play a vital role in e-government systems. According to Ndou (2004), for appropriate sharing of information, there should be good internet access and open up new and accessible communication channels and other online services.

1.1.2. E-governance in Sri Lanka

The evolution of e-governance in Sri Lanka began in 1983. After the Computer Policy for the Development of Communication Technology, the Government of Sri Lanka disclosed the

responsibility of Information and Communication Technology. The Information and Communication Technology Agency of Sri Lanka were established in 2003. The objectives were to build information infrastructure, provide citizen-specific services, enhance ICT's human resources, and create a government that uses ICT for social and economic development. E-Sri Lanka is its initiative, using information and communication technology to reduce poverty in Sri Lanka and develop the Sri Lankan economy. It is the origin of the e-government of Sri Lanka. (Dissanayaka *et al*; 2013). The government of Sri Lanka has launched e-Sri Lankan programs under e-governance that aim to improve public services, uplift citizens' quality of life, achieve economic and social development, and eradicate poverty (Karunasena and Deng, 2010).

Skill and ability to use ICT in Sri Lanka are developing daily. Further, the Sri Lankan government has made significant efforts to develop the skills of its citizens through various e-governance initiatives and activities. There are many examples; likewise, some NENASALA centers also operate as e-libraries for the use of all citizens and have been established and launched in rural areas to develop the ease of government services (Karunasena and Deng, 2010). With the development of Sri Lankan society, the ICT knowledge of citizens is growing with a positive correlation. According to the e-government index, in comparing SAARC regions, Sri Lanka is in second place in the 2010 survey (Fowsar, 2019). It is one of the significant developments in ICT usage in Sri Lanka.

1.1.3. M- Governance

M-governance is one of the sub-domains of e-governance. It ensures that electronic services can reach people via mobile technologies, such as mobile phones. These are primary electronic services that can get usages by citizens in every community, and they are also cheaper as well as accessible easily. According to increasing mobile phone accessibility, governments are promoting services by using the mobile phone to deliver e-governance services.

At the end of 2004, the trend of Internet functionality, applications of mobile phones, and usage of mobile devices increased among residents aged 15 and 75 in Asian countries by nearly 90%. It was discovered that mobile phones could use much more than straightforward communications; likewise, mobile parking, mobile Banking, m-payments, m-democracy, and m-administration. Mobile phones are cheaper, technically inclined, more user-friendly, and easier to devise than computers (Rannu, 2004). As mobile phones can provide fast services to the citizens of all strata, mobile governance has become a well-known concept today. During the past ten years, we have witnessed how mobile phones for voice or text messaging (SMS) and mobile apps empowered citizens to interact with each other and with society. The development of the Sri Lankan government required advanced mobile internet services to develop interconnection and flexible services for citizens, companies, other organizations, and the government. The Sri Lankan government offers these functionalities with high security for customers and data. To develop its benefits, the Sri Lankan government introduced mobile services. Cost Saving, using proficiency, transformation/modernization of the public sector, giving convenience and flexibility services to the citizens, and developing easy interactions were some benefits of mobile governance (Akhtar *et al*; 2019).

Compared to internet services, citizens can get assistance by mobile phones from the government at a lower cost. Even citizens living in most rural or local bodies with a poor understanding of information and communication technologies (ICT) can get m-governance services. The government is trying to reach production in the private sector and introducing SMS services, developed apps, or mobile awareness programs for citizens past (M-govworld.org, 2010).

The number of mobile subscribers within Sri Lanka by the end of 2007 was almost 70 times the number of customers reported a decade back. According to this growth in mobile customer base, Sri Lanka has introduced many supplementary services. Short Message Service (SMS) is one of the accessible services that mobile-based companies have introduced. Not only smart or i-phones but also standard phones can get SMS service for all levels of people, and it has become the primary non-verbal communication channel among

the general public (Wijetunge *et al.*, 2008). Khalil and Kenny in 2008, has introduced four significant factors that made mobile phones a popular item even among rural communities. These are, it can be used irrespective of their poor literacy and income, easy mobility and usage, flexible deployment, and relatively low and declining costs. According to these facilities, mobile phones also use SMS service to extend several exciting benefits to rural communities in various parts of the world.

M-government became more popular than e-government because m-government is the anytime and anywhere concept. However, m-government and e-government are not different concepts, and M-government is an advanced set of e-government now. For example, the m-government can build wireless communication technology among government organizations and share information with citizens and industrial enterprises (Nava and Davila 2005). There are primary purposes of m-government services, such as ensuring mobility for the public, saving time, collecting data efficiently, sharing information, *etc.* (Wijetunge *et al.*, 2008).

Agriculture also plays a dominant role in economic growth and food security in Sri Lanka, and the government has launched these awareness programs for farmers using mobile-based devices. SMS (Short Message Service) is a popular method to inform farmers of yield prediction, price predictions, and crop optimization (Gamage *et al.*, 2021). These examples show that the agriculture field also uses m-governance. Mobile technology is one of the possible solutions to deliver warning notifications and emergency alert information. For example, emergency information about floods, Tsunamis, Landslides, and hurricanes is broadcast by the SMS Alert service in Sri Lanka. The government has recognized that Service is the most suitable way of informing people who live in vulnerable areas (Aloudat *et al.*; 2007). Many government agencies in Sri Lanka are currently using the SMS service to provide information to the public. As the technical literacy of Sri Lanka improves daily, the concepts of good governance and E-governance have evolved. It is gratifying to be able to provide such mobile-based services (Jayasuriya, 2018). Under m- governance, departments and government agencies

in Sri Lanka introduced SMS services to clients who receive services from their organization for various purposes. The Department for Registration of Persons has also introduced this SMS service.

1.1.4. SMS Service of the Department for Registration of Persons, As an M-Government Service

Combined with new technology, the Sri Lankan public service introduced this Service for preparing national identity cards, which can be described as very effective and efficient. This technology helped limit the hours spent manually designing a national identity card, thus saving time. Even if this new technology is used, it will take a minimum of 03 hours to prepare a National Identity Card from the one-day Service, and more than 2,000 applicants will have to stay on the premises daily. After handing over the documents to the division “D” on the 9th floor of the DRP, applicants usually wait until the A division on the 9th floor to obtain their National Identity Cards. The names of the applicants are announced using the loudspeakers. In this way, the Department introduced an SMS alert service to reduce congestion on the premises and develop satisfaction among the applicants as the leading government department of Sri Lanka. Even if the applicant leaves the premises, SMS service is beneficial.

This SMS service is essential to be aware of the dispatch time of their NIC card. The applicant should mention their mobile number in column 11.1 on the third page of the Identity card application. After completing the Identity card process, the applicant will be informed using that number with the assistance of Sri Lanka Telecom Mobitel Pvt. Ltd. The SMS service was launched on 25th of January 2020, in collaboration with SLT Mobitel Pvt. Ltd. In consultation with the Mobitel Company and the Department for Registration of Persons, decided not to charge any additional fee to the public for this other Service. Mobitel introduced a similar service to the Department of Immigration and Emigration on 25th of March 2009. Mobitel has agreed to provide the free SMS service. The Informatics Company has provided full technical support for preparing the National Identity Card based on outsourcing technical assistance required by government agencies. The informatics also

includes personal information (telephone numbers) to Mobitel through a web interface to provide the SMS service and informs them once the National Identity Card has been processed. Even if Mobitel receives applicants' mobile phone numbers systematically in this way, it should evaluate the provision of this Service without infringing on the applicants' privacy. After the applicant submits the applications to the Department, the applicant will receive an SMS informing them that the National Identity Card has been prepared. Mobitel does not charge fees for providing SMS service and only notes "Powered by Mobitel" at the end of the SMS. This SMS is limited to 125 characters and transmitted only in English.

This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the SMS service for registering persons as an m- government service. This service was implemented on 25/01/2020. At least 1000 SMSs daily, 22000 SMS s per month, and 264000 SMSs per year. The cost of the Mobitel Company is $0.15 \times 1000 = 150.00$ per day and $33000.00 \times 12 = 396,000.00$ per year. However, this service is provided to the general public for free, and the government should effectively provide this kind of m-governance service.

1.2. Research Problem

1.2.1. Problem Identification

In establishing coordination between the government and the citizens, the SMS service is essential to use in the services provided by the government. Promoting such services activates the concept of a mobile state in Sri Lanka; the Department for Registration of Persons also implements a short message service to inform the applicants once the process of their National Identity Card has been finalized and report them to collect it. The Service was introduced as required to increase public satisfaction with the government service of the DRP and forward short messages with commands to collect Identity cards while controlling the crowd within the premises. Since the text messaging service has been available for two years, it should now check whether it has achieved the desired objectives.

1.2.2. Problem Justification

Citizens have expected ICT-based Services as the subsequent overwhelming penetration of mobile phones in developing countries. Therefore, mobile-based services can be identified as an alternative to disseminating information in Sri Lanka. Currently, a few mobile-based SMS services, such as TRI SMS service, Twitter Information Service for rural communities, SMS service for kidney patients of Kandy hospital, and many other government SMS services, can be seen in Sri Lanka.

"Sri Lanka Dialog Govi Mithuru " voice message services are available in Sri Lanka. Also, users of these mobile-based SMS services have to pay or not for the Service. The mobile-based SMS service is applicable in a wide range of knowledge dissemination and is an effective way of fulfilling the receivers' needs by sending the latest information. The tea sector is using these services, and consequently, it has revealed a more significant potential to increase the overall efficiency of the tea industry (Weerasinghe and Mudalige, 2010). In addition, mobile phones are effectively used to meet the information needs of rural communities in various contexts. The Ipalogama Vidatha Resource Center in Sri Lanka has also evaluated the effectiveness of a mobile phone-based Twitter information delivery service using the technology acceptance model. Such systems are helpful, easy to use, and cost-effective in meeting requirements (Wijerathna *et al.*, 2020).

Nearly 1000 applicants come to DRP to make their National Identity Cards from one-day Service per day. DRP has provided SMS service under the M-Governance since 2020 and they were collaborating with SLT Mobitel. Pvt. Ltd, However, there is a lack of attempts to assess the level of mobile - based SMS usage by the DRP. There was a main purpose in this Service, to develop the satisfaction of the applicants. It has not been evaluated to see whether the SMS service of DRP delivered the expected outcomes yet. This study attempts to fill this research gap by assessing the effectiveness of the mobile-based SMS service introduced by DRP.

1.3. Research Question

Explain the Effectiveness of the SMS alert service by the Department for Registration of Persons in Sri Lanka.

1.4. Research Objectives

1.4.1. General Objective

Evaluate the effectiveness of the SMS service of the DRP as an M-Governance service.

1.4.2. Specific Objectives

1. Evaluate the usage of the SMS service of the DRP
2. Evaluate the level of satisfaction of users of the SMS service of DRP
3. Study factors affecting the use of services operated by DRP.
4. Explain the problems and limitations faced by the user community of the current SMS alert service provided by DRP.
5. Provide recommendations to improve the SMS service implemented by DRP.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This study investigated the effectiveness of the SMS service introduced by the DRP and investigated the success of the SMS service as an m-governance method through a literature review. How e-government services have developed with the ICT and the benefits of SMS service with the spread of the m-government concept are identified from the literature reviews.

2.2. ICT in Sri Lanka

In studying information regarding ICT use in Sri Lanka, several studies conducted in Sri Lanka were used to study the extent to which ICT is used not only by the general public but also by government officials and government agencies. The ICT policy of Sri Lanka has received a lot of input from local and international institutions, and it has been analyzed that the country needs to improve its quality and provide a sustainable start (Ravindra, 2011). The author reviewed the secondary data, and the initiation of ICT policy is entirely focused on its development. In particular, data from Sri Lanka has explored how ICT integrates with education, government, industry, and the public. It has provided an overview of success in the ICT sector of Sri Lanka. As a result of the research, the importance of strategically implementing ICT has been taught, the contribution to the country's development plans has been analyzed, and the actions to be taken in the future to expand opportunities for the third world. Moreover, this study has also sought solutions to the national problems faced by Sri Lanka in the progress of information and communication technology and the use of CT.

Accordingly, after evaluating the Information and Communication Technology policy of Sri Lanka, it has been found that the approach is highly comprehensive. It has been revealed that it should comprehensively contribute to socioeconomic development and directly to the

education, health, and entrepreneurship sectors. It was discovered that ICT could contribute to solving the problem of poverty in Sri Lanka, build closer relationships using technology, and provide services to the public by the government. In this context, it was suggested that the Sri Lanka Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (TRC) should improve the IT system in Sri Lanka. Then it is revealed that as a future country in Asia, Sri Lanka can benefit from information and communication technology. It was also informed that Sri Lanka would become an economic and political benchmark in the world by implementing the lessons from ICT in Sri Lanka.

In analyzing information and communication technology in Sri Lanka, Done by Samansiri and Wanigasundara has revealed some critical information about Sri Lankan ICT in 2014. This study has contributed to improving the earnings of agribusinesses in Sri Lanka using technology and understanding its current situation. The study revealed information and communication technology (ICT) among small tea plantation owners and workers. It was found that most ICT users in the Sri Lankan industry are above 36 years of age and educated people with more than 20 years of work experience. According to them, a significant development in the use of telephones as all the respondents owned mobile phones and had access to landlines. It has also been revealed that younger people use technology such as the Internet and e-mail. However, the use of these facilities is less among elderly extension workers. Accordingly, the research has shown that using technology and ICT will lead to development in the tea industry and the business sector in Sri Lanka.

2.3. Identifying E-government

The concept of e-government has become a trendy concept in the world today, and it helps provide services to transparent public services using technology. For this research, as studies related to the concept of e-government were conducted, attention was paid to several studies that have been conducted on its trends. Every sector is now using technology to transform the way people live, the way they work, the way companies do business, and the way governments serve their people. As technology has become the only principle supporting the

e-business revolution, citizen-centric service and information provision have evolved the concept of e-government today. Hence, the use of technology to provide information and public services to citizens (G2C), businesses (G2B), government employees, or other government agencies (G2G) is called e-government (Susanto *et al*; 2008). E-government provides transparent and accountable services with easy and fast information access. The studies by Malagon. have discovered in 2010, that e-government has the potential to provide services and information to the public and to carry out e-democracy through the direct participation of citizens. E-governance can be done not only through the government's website but also through technical means such as e-mail and digital or electronic access. New concept of e-government is essential for building a relationship between citizens and the government. E-government has many benefits as it allows citizens to communicate with the government, and e-Government can empower citizens, reduce government corruption, provide transparent service, increase convenience, increase revenue and reduce government costs (Susanto *et al*; 2008).

The motivation factors for citizens to use SMS-based e-government services have shown that there are fifteen perceptions or internal aspects of SMS usage. Susanto and Goodwin in 2010, uncovered reasons that influence citizens to use or reject text messaging services provided by the government to the public. Accordingly, the study has revealed that factors such as ease of use of e-government services, time spent on delivering services, efficiency, the usefulness of the service, quality of information, and reliability affect the use of SMS technology. In addition, it has been found that there is self-efficacy in using SMS and that awareness must be provided to motivate a citizen to adopt an SMS-based e-government service. Social cognition, age, and gender of citizens affected the usage of e-government SMS services. It was revealed that intensive advertising should be done in all mass media channels, and confidence should be built among the citizens regarding the service. Accordingly, it has been revealed in the study that governments should provide the necessary environment to establish SMS-based e-government services, etc., to develop computer literacy and technical literacy in a country.

2.4. E-governance in Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is a developing country. Instances such as civil war significantly hampered the development of ICT. Modern technology is essential to improve public service delivery with support from significant international funds and organizations, so the Government of Sri Lanka launched e-government services. Accordingly, to bring about economic and social development, the e-Sri Lanka program was launched in 2002. Therefore, Sri Lanka is expected to develop quickly through e-government policies(Hannah, 2007). Millions of dollars have been invested in ICT development and implementing e-government services in Sri Lanka. The Information and Communication Technology Agency (ICTA) has been established under the e-Sri Lanka program to facilitate the implementation and coordination e- government programs in Sri Lanka (ICTA, 2005).

In the study of Karunasenain 2010, the technological development and initiatives that have taken place in Sri Lanka using the concept of e-government were discovered. Several e-government-related studies conducted in Sri Lanka have studied how e-government services are used in Sri Lanka. Based on this research data, an empirical study has been shown to assess the public value of e-government. It has been revealed that e-Government in Sri Lanka has become underutilized. This research has revealed that e-government services in Sri Lanka have not made significant cost savings, and e-government services have not made tremendous progress. While Sri Lanka ranks 116th in the United Nations Participation Index, it has been revealed in this research that there is no significant improvement in the use of e-services. Fowsarand Sajeethain 2020 attempted to identify the factors determining access to e-services in selected Divisional Secretariats in the Ampara district. It also recalled low access to e-services due to "difficulties of understanding" and "concerns about security." Research revealed that to increase access to e-services by mitigating the effects of these two factors, people need to be more aware and maintain the confidentiality of information. Furthermore, it has been emphasized that public institutions can increase access by giving more publicity to e-services and that it is the government's responsibility to increase efficiency and transparency.

2.5. Identifying M-Government

M-government extends the service and information to poor citizens who are unable to access Public services by using the internet (Deep and Sahoo, 2011). Reported benefits associated with implementing m-government are increasing profitability, improving government performance, improving the quality of service, and improving the effectiveness of service quality and public services. (Jahanshahi *et al.*, 2011). Mobile Government (m-Government) is the government practice. Opportunities and challenges to delivering mobile government services in developing countries were studied in 2009. M-Government has been used as a strategic choice for governments to deliver their businesses and services. (OECD, 2011). As the concept of m-governance has emerged through e-government services, the purpose of implementing m-government services is to enhance the e-governance system (Jahanshahi *et al.*, 2011). Efficiency, service quality, interaction, and justice are the values of m-government determined by the four main factors.(Wang *et al*; 2012).

Kesavarapu and Choi in2012, also conducted a similar study by providing m-government services. Trust, content quality, and system quality are the inclusion of factors such as personalization has been reported to increase public use. These services are being launched to provide standard and quick services to citizens and companies in government administration. This was revealed by Mengistu and Rho, 2009. Their research has found that the m-government methodology is suitable for providing reliable and instant service while avoiding the challenges faced in providing information and services to citizens, businesses, and civil society. M-government could be applied for four primary purposes such as m-services, m-communications, m-governance, and m-democracy in the public sector(Mengistu *et al*; 2007). The use of wireless technology devices is overgrowing worldwide, and it has been revealed that the use of mobile phones has increased even in rural and urban areas of developing countries. Rho in 2009 has shown that the provision of e-government and m-government services has become somewhat tricky in developing countries due to the lack of adequate telecommunication infrastructure, and therefore m-government has implemented

service provision in three different phases. Applications should be tailored to reach citizens. More interactive m-government applications can be developed to allow citizen participation, and highly interactive m-government applications can be developed. (Mengistu *et al*; 2009). M- Government aims to provide equitable technology services to all people. Faced as the m-government took up the challenge of delivering a suitable technological environment for people with disabilities (Kreps, 2010).

The research of Akhtar *et al.*, have revealed the moderating role of cultural values and rapid development of smartphone technology in Asian countries in 2019. The researchers observed cultural values and social impact as a factor undermining the positive relationship between the motivation to use individual m-government services. Nava and Davila in 2005, introduced the differences between technologies and new mobile technologies. This has also emphasized how information Society and m-Government will facilitate citizens. They have studied to understand the concept of a digital city, identity and organize the participants, determine the community's needs, and control or evaluate. They have discovered reasons to reject the governance concept by the citizens. They were security risks, privacy threats, unstable limits, and data electric power consumption.

The government provides short messaging services as a warning alert. While governments have long used broadcast media such as radio and television during emergencies, the study suggests that using technology to deliver up-to-date information to citizens should be done in real-time (Michaeland Ya, 2007). In emergency management techniques, the government has recognized that using early warning text messages to inform the public can bring many benefits to the public. Although SMS is used for public awareness, especially during emergencies and disasters, it is challenging to provide SMS services due to technical breakdowns and the topography of the areas where people in danger stay temporarily. Still, it has been discovered that SMS is very suitable for early notifications. However, Michael and Yan, J have recognized factors such as the educational level, age, technology usage, living area, etc., of using the government's SMS services.

2.6. M- government in Sri Lanka

With the growth of the mobile consumer base, many supplementary services have been introduced, and the EMA study has confirmed that SMS is a significant penetration in Sri Lankan society. SMS has become the main non-verbal communication channel among ordinary people, and it has been discovered that the cost-effectiveness of the SMS service has led to its popularity in Sri Lanka. In this study, Wijethungeet *al.*, examined Sri Lanka's adoption of SMS. This research has analyzed the reasons for the popularity of government SMS services in Sri Lanka and their social impact.

This study has been conducted on patient awareness about SMS service to prevent complications by providing continuous care and awareness by Premadasa in 2021. According to the study's results, a positive relationship has been revealed between the usages of SMS in Sri Lanka. However, Premadasa in 2021 has shown that to use these services provided by the government to the public under the concept of m-government, the people must have technical literacy and use of mobile phones. SMS can be used to exchange information and communicate using mobile phones, which are portable devices. In creating coordination between government authorities and citizens, information is exchanged through SMS as m-government services. Low cost and ease of use are increasingly considered in providing services through SMS (Porte, 2011).

2.7. E- Government based - SMS service

The study of Rannu and Semevsky, 2016 has revealed that Estonia has achieved remarkable success among countries using e-government. Accordingly, this study has been conducted to study the key factors influencing the success of e-government. His study also reveals that the evolution of e-government is mainly based on information. It has been revealed the motivation to use e-government services has increased due to the high competence of providers in the use of innovation and the ability to provide infrastructure. Concerning the use of text messages Maggay, J evaluated the usability of the SMS-based automatic reply

inquiry system in the Usability Evaluation of SMS-Based System research in 2019. In this study, it has been discovered that SMS usability, Ease of use, and Usefulness. SMS service Perceived usefulness of SMS services and defined satisfaction of the users. The end of the adoption and use of systems has been defined with user satisfaction. As a result of the usability evaluation, it was revealed that the SMS-based inquiry system is easy to learn, easy to use, and useful, but it gets easier with practice. Additionally, the system has been found to be flexible, accurate, and reliable, as any mobile phone can be used. Texting is the fastest-growing form of communication nowadays. In the United States, 75 billion text messages were sent in June 2008 alone (Steinhauer & Holson, 2008). When comparing the call volume of mobile users, on average, a mobile user used more SMS than phone calls. (Nielsen News, 2008). The use of text messages is used in the political sphere. The most notable text message was President Barack Obama Used in an election campaign. (Wortham, 2009).

2.8. Adaption for Mobile based SMS services

Mobile service adoption can be attributed to several factors, such as personal and social factors, technology level, and education literacy. Many researchers have evaluated the theoretical foundations to explore the mobile service adoption factors, and prior research on technology adoption was reviewed. According to Mennecke and Strader in 2003, several theories were developed to help explain the concept of technology adoption. Not only is the approach of Mennecke, but there is also a Technology acceptance model by Davies 1989. It has introduced the relationship between users' usage and adaptation of technology. Research has revealed that user acceptance patterns for text messaging services have changed. In the study, Gong and Thong revealed in 2005 that these changes occur through the framework of information technology acceptance. Technological factors are the main drivers of user acceptance of SMS and are studied using a theoretical framework.

The level of development, cultural differences, political factors, language, and gender influence the use of text messages provided by the government (Mennecke and Strader, 2003). Under TAM, the study has been conducted using factors such as perceived usefulness,

ease of use, attitudes, and behavioral Intention. It has been reported that the advancement in technology has a positive effect on the use of SMS as it influences the improvement in the use of SMS. Factors related to consumer adoption of short message services have been analyzed in the study by Park in 2008. It has been identified that perceived enjoyment (PENJ), perceived ease of use (PEU), perceived monetary value (PMV), and perceived usefulness (PU) are four significant factors that directly affect mobile phone users and SMS adaptation. Hong and Tam, in 2006, studied the factors influencing the use of mobile services by twenty individuals using TAM and several studies based on other theories. Their study investigated the desire to adopt technology, Perceived nature, satisfaction to receive technical services, Value for money and gender were found to be significant. Xu and Wang conducted a study in 2002 to investigate the use of SMS by consumers. In this study, the main factors of using SMS have been studied. The study hypothesis is developed by examining several cases from Finland, Japan, and the United States. M-government is booming due to the low cost of using SMS services, how mobile phones are used, effective marketing, and government support. Similarly, the natures of the social system and service environment, user satisfaction, etc., affect the use of government-provided SMS services (Wang and Hausman, 2006). Kleinrock, in 1996, described the benefits provided by mobile technologies as "anytime and anywhere use." The government is providing services to the public in dealing with commerce by getting rid of traditional electronic methods. Computerization gives users more freedom, and their ability to access information and services has improved. However, Kakihara and Sorensen, in 2000, argued that geographical boundaries, human interaction, network provision, ease of use of services, usefulness, and education level are the reasons for using m-government services.

Based on the above theories and research, has been developed conceptual framework. The influences of internal, external, and technological factors on the impact of SMS service usage and user satisfaction are studied through a conceptual framework. The study by Susanto and Goodwin, 2010 also found that external and internal factors influence the use of text messaging services.

2.9. Conceptual Framework

Age, gender, education, and English language skills were studied under the internal factors, while the awareness of the SMS service and the living area were studied as the external factors. The extent of Use of mobile messages was studied based on operating a mobile phone, reading SMS, and being familiar with using SMS. The usage of SMS service was studied based on the temptation to use the SMS service provided by DRP. User satisfaction has been measured through the ease of Use and usefulness of the SMS service of DRP.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This research primarily studied the extent to which the Short Message Service provided by the Department for Registration of Persons, based on the concept of mobile government, has been effective. Five variables were studied under a conceptual framework based on the Technology Acceptance model. Three independent variables and two dependent variables have been used in the research to construct the conceptual framework. Qualitative and quantitative data were collected using questionnaires. In addition, effects of some demographic factors have been evaluated as independent variables after studying several successful types of research and comparative analysis with this research. Telephone interviews were conducted using the developed questionnaire and collected primary data from 150 respondents.

3.2. Identification of the research population

The study community were the public that apply NIC through the one-day service. Sample frame of the study were the applicants who came to prepare National ID cards under one-day service during the month of August 2022 (From 01/08/2022 to 31/08/2022). The total number of applicants during the month of August were 18,128.

3.3. Selection of the sample

Before sampling, it had preconceived about how many people should be chosen as gender and age-wise for the sample. Applicants must reserve a date for obtaining National ID cards, and the list of daily applicants has also been systemized. Using that list, stratified the applicants according to gender and age before arranging the sample. It has categorized each 75 of both sexes and prepared two categories of ages below 30 years and over 30 years.

Selecting 37 or 38 from each age group was reasonable sample stratification. Accordingly a total of 150 respondents were selected as the sample. Each day, 8/ 10th number of respondents were selected and interviewed using telephone interviews.

people were selected randomly, questioned from among those segments, and collected data. Stratified random sampling was done in this research because several males, females, and several age applicants come to the DRP, and there are different age groups. Therefore, the study aimed to improve sampling accuracy and reduce sampling errors. Fabio *et al*; also studied, in 2018, the effectiveness of the short notice service using stratified samples for collecting data, and they mentioned that stratification is an easy way to reach all groups of samples.

3.4. Data collection method

This descriptive study used a Telephone survey questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The questionnaire is a structured technique for data collection consisting of a series of questions, written or verbal, that a respondent answers (Malhotra and Peterson, 1999). A total of 21 questions were used to collect primary data measuring user satisfaction. The study used a three-part questionnaire. The first part was a questionnaire that measured the basic profile of the respondents, and it could have calculated the environmental factors of the conceptual framework. The second part of the questionnaire contained questions to measure the usability of mobile phones, ease of use, the usefulness of SMS service, and satisfaction. There were 12 statements using five-point Likert scale questions.

The third part of the questionnaire contains two open-ended questions to measure the problems of the DRP SMS service and comments and suggestions to improve the service. Apart from primary data, data was collected through secondary media such as the internet, newspapers, magazines, etc. to verify the collected data's accuracy and analysis.

The research data was collected using questionnaires, and the questionnaires were arranged in the following manner so that all the independent and dependent variables of the conceptual framework has represented in Table 01.

Table 1: Independent and Dependent variables

Variables	factors	Measure by questionnaire	Number of statements or questions
Independent Variables	internal factors	Gender	1
		Age	1
		Education Level	1
		English Language Skill	2
	External Factors	Awareness	3
		Living Area	1
	Technological Factors	can operate a mobile phone, use mobile SMSs, read SMS and familiar with using SMS	4
Dependent Variables	Usage Of SMS Service	Temptation to use DRP SMS Service	1
	User Satisfaction, Ease of use, Usefulness,	User Satisfaction	4

3.5. Data analysis

Data were tabulated and analyzed by using MS Excel, and parametric and non-parametric statistical tests were run in SPSS 16.0 software. The descriptive method was also used to analyze descriptive data.

In this study, a questionnaire was used to collect data, and the aim was to conclude from the information or data. Accordingly, the validity and reliability of the data set were checked from the collected data through the questionnaire. Further, construct validity is suggested based on the factor loading estimates, creating reliabilities, and developing the inter-construct correlations (Hair *et al*; 2006). For this instrument, Cronbach's Alpha was 0.902 and 0.000 significance level $p < 0.005$. If all coefficient alpha estimates were more significant than 0.74, they were considered within the acceptable range (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Accordingly, the internal consistency has been excellent, and the research tool has given credible results.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Introduction

This study investigated the usage of the SMS service of the DRP and the user satisfaction of applicants who used the one-day service. In this descriptive research, an attempt has been made to identify the extent to which the SMS service introduced by the Department for Registration of Persons has succeeded in the mobile government concept. The people and the government or government agencies will benefit from raising a text message service (Susanto and Calder, 2008).

Based on the concept of mobile government, this SMS service is provided by DRP to the public. If this service is effective, applicants should use the m-governance technology of DRP and be satisfied with the service. Similar research conducted by Rannu and Semevsky in 2005 has revealed that demographic, internal, external, and technical factors affect the public's satisfaction when providing new services to the government. Accordingly, this chapter has classified and analyzed the collected data from the applicants, along with internal, external, and technological factors, to measure the effectiveness of the usage of the short message service introduced by the DRP.

4.2. Characteristics of the user community

The research of Mandari *et al*, in 2007 has been monitored using Stratified and multi-stage sampling with simple random samples for their study because it is easy to measure the response of all communities. The two factors of gender and age have shown a similar distribution because of obtained mainly by stratified sample. As the minimum age for preparation of National Identity Cards is 15 years, the age levels of the respondents were divided into below 30 years and above 30 years.

75 males under 30 years of age and 75 men above age 30 and also 75 women over 30 years of age, and 75 women under 30 years of age were collected.

Table .02 shows the demographic data of the 125 applicants who received the SMS alert of DRP out of 150 that were selected as the sample. According to these findings 125 people have used the SMS service provided by the Department for Registration of Persons. There were (n=63)50.5% males and (n=62) 49.5% female respondents. In terms of percentage, males have a higher rate of using this kind of technology introduced by the government. Therefore, it was inferred that people with credibility regarding this text message service provided by DRP under the concept of m- governance would use the text message service. According to this study, out of the 125 people, 64 people 51% were in the age group below 30 years old, and 61 people, which are about 49.5%, were identified as being in the age group above 30 years old. Accordingly, it can be concluded that the use of mobile government applications with new technologies is more among the younger generation of people less than 30 years of age.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to receive of DRP SMS

Gender and age		Frequency %
Gender	Male	50.5
	Female	49.5
Age Level	Below 30 years	51
	Above 30 years	49

A study by Susanto and Goodwin in 2008 reported that as citizen's age, there is a greater awareness of and willingness of elders to adopt SMS-based e-government services; because their experiences, usability, and knowledge of technology are higher than low age groups. Still, the findings of this study have shown that a greater propensity for m-governance applications could be seen in those below 30 years of age group (15-30 age group). The study published by Chen, in 2017 and according to Susanto and Goodwin in 2008 revealed that men are more interested in using e-governance services than women. Accordingly, this research also discovered that the response level was higher in men than in women. It can be

concluded that technology usage and new mobile-based innovations are used by the new male generation.

According to table 06, there were 25 applicants who had not received the SMS service can be seen out of a 150 sample. According to table 03, it was discovered that (n=12) 45% of males had not been tempted to use the DRP SMS service, and (n=13) 55% of females also had not used it. The rejection level of new technology has increased for females than males, and m-governance service has been rejected by older females (above 30 years) than young level (below 30 years) males. It has been shown as follows.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to non-received of DRP SMS

	Gender and age	Frequency %
Gender	Male	45
	Female	55
Age Level	Below 30 years	44
	Above 30 years	56

4.3. Factors affecting the use of SMS service

Although the demographic factors such as gender and age discussed above were studied under the internal factors, mainly the respondents' educational level and English language ability were examined under the internal factors. Does the education level of the public influence the usage of the SMS service introduced by DRP as an m-governance service? Was the SMS service the government provided effective or ineffective for a person with a low education level was investigated? The level of awareness about the SMS service of DRP, the effect of the living area of Respondents for SMS usage, and technological factors were also studied.

4.3.1. Level of Education

Accordingly, the educational level of the 125 respondents who had to tempt to use the SMS service from the selected sample was considered. In addition, Walter *et al*; examined in 2012 the effectiveness of the education level of the respondents in text message usage. They have revealed that there may be a positive or negative or non-relationship between the use of SMS and the respondent's Education level. In the e-governance and mobile phone usage study in Rwanda, and Donner, identified in 2010 that a group of education affects mobile application usage. It has been analyzed that people with good education also stand out in using technology services such as SMS service as it is easier for people with higher levels of education to use technology.

The educational level of the respondents was measured as an independent variable in this study. Furthermore, the effect of the applicants' education level was also studied using the SMS service introduced by DRP as an m-governance service. In segmenting the level of education, Frias *et al*; in their study, divided into primary, secondary, and tertiary groups. But in this study, the education level of respondents was divided into 04 segments, namely primary education, education up to Ordinary level, education up to Advanced level, and higher education.

Accordingly, in this study, the educational groups of the 125 people who tended to use the SMS service and the 25 who did not use the SMS service were examined separately. According to the sample of 125, 43 (34%) of the people had higher education, 41 (35%) had studied up to Advanced Level, 36 (29%) had studied up to ordinary level, and 2 (2%) had studied primary education. It is shown in figure 01.

Education Level of SMS users

Figure 1: Distribution of SMS users by the level of education

Accordingly, to further study whether there is an effect of the level of education for SMS usage as an m-governance service, has also been studied the level of education of the sample of 25 who were not tempted to use the SMS service provided by the DRP. Out of the sample, 2 (8%) belong to the segment that has studied primary education, 12 (48%) of the people have studied up to the Ordinary level, 10 (40%) have studied up to the advanced level, and 1 (4%) of the people have higher education. It is also indicated by figure 02.

Education Level of SMS non-users

Figure 2: Distribution of SMS non-users by the level of education

People with higher levels of education are more likely to use technology services due to higher levels of experience and ability, and willingness to use technology (Frias *et al.*, 2012). Accordingly, this study has shown that people with good educational levels have more intention to get this kind of m-governance service, and people with lower academic levels have less will to get this kind of m-governance service.

4.3.2. English Language Skill

English is an international language. The SMS service of DRP is sent in the English language because applicants are speaking in different languages. The maximum number of characters was 25 in the SMS. That is why sending text messages in the three main languages of Sinhala, Tamil, and English is impossible. This service is provided in the English language only, assuming that the English language is easy for everyone to use.

Although many government departments are seen sending text messages printed in English with a Sinhala accent, this SMS service is only in English for the convenience of all Sri Lankans. Jaworski and Thurlow, have revealed in his study that printing in English and using the pronunciation of another language harms the English language and helps to kill the English language. Therefore, his study further revealed in 2010 that the correct terminology to be used in English is a technical device for sending a short message. Furthermore, Durke *et al;* in 2012 found that English literacy skills influence text message comprehension and usage. The study also revealed that young people with better English literacy skills used relatively higher text message usage. Accordingly, this study investigated whether English language skills affect the use of the SMS service sent to the public for informing the preparation of National Identity Cards.

In 2013, Verheijen found a positive correlation between English literacy and text message usage. But further revealing, Verheijen states that there are studies that have found no negative or significant correlation between English literacy and texting and that the correlation between individual literacy and texting may vary depending on the nature of the sample. The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship ($r=0.404$, $p= 0.000$) between in English Literacy and usage of DRP SMS service. Accordingly, as revealed in this study, it is shown a moderate but positive correlation between English reading skills and DRP SMS service.

Therefore, this study revealed that as English literacy increases, the use of SMS services increases. This study has measured English literacy and temptation to use English SMS using a Likert scale question. "I can read and understand short text messages written in English" means the figure 03. Accordingly, it was discovered that (n=45)30% have given answers as strongly agree, (n=61) 41% have given answers as Agree, (n=29) 19% have given answers as neutral, (n=10) 7% have answered as disagree, and (n=5) 3% have given answers as strongly disagree regarding sending text messages in English.

Ability to read and understand SMS

Figure 3 :Distribution of respondents about the ability to read and understand SMS in English

Among the respondents, a sample of 125 who have been motivated to use the SMS service of DRP, the question of the Likert format was asked. "I found it very difficult to understand the message as it was in English". For that, (n=58)46 % disagreed. Providing the SMS service in English has not been a problem for them at all. (n=36) 29% have given answers as strongly disagree.(n=24) 19% have given answers as neutral, and (n=3+4) 6% have given answers as Agree and Strongly Agree. It was revealed that about 6% felt uncomfortable because the text message was sent in English.

However, Kemp and Bushnell found in 2011, that those with better English literacy skills had higher speed and accuracy in reading text messages. According to table 04, there were identified five people, (17%) who expressed disapproval of reading SMS messages in English.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents who did not use the SMS Service of DRP

Factor	Frequency %
Problem Of Phone	10
Useless. Come back evening to collect the ID card	21
Another owner of the Phone	21
Do not know to check SMS	17
Do not Know English to read SMS	17
Do not Sure this Government service	14

In 2010, Neville's and Kemp's findings also revealed that when using text messages, reading and understanding the text messages sent in English is relatively slow. Accordingly, in providing such an m-governance service, appropriate solutions should be obtained according to the needs of the general public. Mr. Deram. P, an executive manager of Sri Lanka Telecom Mobitel, Pvt. (Ltd.), informed that there is no charge for this text message service, and the department should pay an additional amount for sending the text message in three languages because of over character limits. Accordingly, it is revealed some people have faced language problems when they use this service. Therefore, the Department of Registration of Persons should provide proper awareness regarding the SMS sent to the public. Or the purpose of the service provided will not be fulfilled.

4.3.3. Awareness

When the government introduces new technology, if there is no proper awareness about it, there is no tendency to use the technology or to use new inputs. That is why V. Pardeshi introduced in 2010 that stakeholders should increase awareness to show high motivation for m-Government activities. Accordingly, to increase the adoption of SMS-based e-government services, the government should advertise the services to ensure people are aware of them (Susanto and Goodwin, 2010). However, referring to the Diffusion of Innovation theory, the Hierarchy-of-Effects, and the Stage-of-Change models, awareness is the main point for adaptation (Rogers and Prochaska, 2003).

Accordingly, individuals' decisions toward using an SMS-based e-government service require more stages than just awareness; each step involves various factors (Susanto and Goodwin, 2010). However, it was primarily studied whether there was a correlation between the "awareness method" and the usage of SMS service by the DRP. It was discovered that when the level of awareness was high, the temptation to use the SMS service of DRP increased. Accordingly, as revealed in this study, it is shown that there is a moderate and positive correlation between Awareness and usage of DRP SMS service. The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship between approaches ($r=0.584$, $p=0.000$) in usage of SMS service of DRP and awareness.

In this study, the respondents' awareness of DRP text message service was primarily determined using two questions.

1. Were you aware of the DRP SMS Service?
2. I was satisfied with the awareness of the SMS service of the DRP (Likert Scale Question).

When analyzing the preliminary results of awareness and usage of e-government services, it has also been inquired which party was aware of this SMS service. In this research, the respondents were asked about their satisfaction with awareness of the SMS service introduced by DRP using a Likert-style question. Regarding this SMS service, which DRP introduced as an m-Government service, it has primarily investigated respondents' awareness. Rogers in 2003 suggested that innovation's success also depends on others' awareness process, primarily through communication channels.

Susanto conducted a similar study in 2010, collecting data from 25 countries on the extent to which individual awareness is required to motivate the use of SMS service provided by the e-government concept. His research data investigated the awareness and adoption of SMS-based e-government services. However, through this study, the respondents' awareness of DRP SMS services has been examined separately. Accordingly, in this research, the awareness and the usage of SMS the service of DRP is shown in figure 04, 83% of the

sample respondents have used SMS services. Out of the rest, 4% had been aware but did not use the services, and the remaining 13% had not been aware and had not used the SMS-based m-government service of DRP.

Figure 4: Distribution of respondents about Usage of the DRP SMS service

It was concluded that many people have become aware of the SMS service. According to Figure 05, (n=107) 41% have been aware of the SMS service of DRP from the DRP announcements, and (n=85) 33% from officers who accepted /authorized applications in DRP. However, (n=30) 11% and (n=22) 8% applicants have been aware of the SMS service from the Grama Niladhari and development officers in the Divisional Secretariats. The remaining (n=17)7% have been aware of the SMS service of DRP from the other parties who came to get the National ID card from the one-day service SMS or from people who used this service before or from any party who was aware of DRP's SMS service.

aware of the SMS service of DRP

Figure 5: Awareness methods about DRP SMS service

Accordingly, in the data analysis of this study, it was revealed that most people became aware of the SMS service of DRP after submitting their applications to the department. Therefore, when completing the application, the applicant should mention the specific phone number or a phone number where they can receive a text message. Because even when informed by DRP notifications made after applying, the phone number given by the applicant may not be correct or his own.

Therefore, the next step was to study the sample unaware of the SMS service of DRP. From that group, (n=11) 7% applicants did not have a mobile phones. Although they did not have a mobile phone, they could not receive text messages as the phone number of a relative or friend was mentioned in the application. After contacting the applicants for the telephone interview using the telephone numbers mentioned in the application form, it was revealed that they had not been informed about the mobile phone number to be mentioned when filling out the application form or about these SMS services. Therefore, they often mention in the application the mobile phone number at home or the phone number of their close friend or relatives.

There were 25 respondents who did not receive the Short message provided by DRP and were unaware about the SMS service. 06 applicants had not opened the text message, and 19 applicants did not know whether they had received a text message. Nevertheless, all the 06 applicants who did not receive the SMS had mobile phones, but only 03 of them were aware of the SMS service. The 49th respondent, the 86th respondent, and the 94th respondent have responded as follows. All three have been aware of the SMS service of DRP from DRP announcements and DRP officers.

49- "It must be a network problem. I did not receive the SMS sent by DRP."

86- "I don't know how to view text messages. So I was not interested in that".

94- ""I was waiting for my name to be announced. A text message had been received. But there was no interest in checking."

There were 19 applicants unaware of DRP's SMS services, 8 had mobile phones, but 11 did not. Although by calling the mobile phone number mentioned in the application form, the sample people were contacted, they said, "this phone number is not mine, but I noted this in the application form." Thus, the SMS service provided by DRP as an m-government service may not be 100% effective due to not being informed that the correct phone number should be mentioned in the application.

The other statement that was used in the questionnaire when asking about Awareness, "I was satisfied with Awareness about the SMS service of the DRP." (Likert-Scale Question). According to figure 06, (n=43) 29% of respondents were strongly agreed regarding the satisfaction of individual Awareness regarding the SMS service provided by DRP. (n=65), 40% were agreed, and (n=22), 15% were neutral. (n=10+5) 16% were disagreed and strongly disagreed. This revealed that although many people are aware of the DRP SMS service if they were aware before filling out the application form, they could have availed of it by specifying the correct phone numbers.

User satisfaction with the awareness

Figure 6: Distribution of respondents of DRP, by the level of satisfaction with the awareness of DRP SMS service

Accordingly, initial awareness regarding DRP's SMS service should be given at the time of application completion and at the time of application certification. That is, the awareness should be done in the first few stages. Such awareness can increase the satisfaction of service recipients as well as the effectiveness of the service.

4.3.4. Living Area

In using text message services for sharing information with the government, it has been investigated how to influence respondents' living areas for the usage of DRP SMS. In data collection, the living areas of the respondents for the telephone interview were examined as follows.

1. Urban
2. Close to town
3. Slightly out of town
4. Very far from the city

The extent to which the area of residence influences the usage of SMS service provided by the DRP was analyzed. According to the study of Mthokozisi and Moherndran, there was a high frequency of SMS message usage in rural areas compared to urban areas. Despite high ownership, participants in the urban areas had not much-used text messages. However, most urban areas were willing to use e-mobile technology to access healthcare.

This study examined which geographical areas the SMS service introduced by DRP as an m-governance service was widely used, and it has been mentioned in table 05.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by Living area

Factor	%
urban	27
close to town	46
slightly out of town	16
very far from the city	11

People who have lived close to town areas have been more tempted to use this text messaging service than others as they are intertwined with technology. Thus, people in rural

areas have less usage of government-provided SMS services. But relatively, people living slightly out of town have used the SMS service provided by DRP more than rural people because it is a convenient method and a technology to communicate with them. According to Mthokozisi's 2019 study, rural people tend to use government-directed SMS services compared to urban people because they are less inclined to use internet technology. Urban people were informed that the importance given to SMS is less because they use the Internet more than SMS. But this research reveals that the SMS service of DRP is used much by people who live close to towns and cities.

4.3.5. Use of SMS

Based on the ability and interest of an individual to use SMS, it was studied how the applicants are tempted to use the SMS introduced by DRP. Seranko and Warshaw in 2007, discovered people who use text messaging or mobile phone technology are more likely to adopt SMS-based new technology services. Therefore, people who use SMS were focused on the services provided. In this study, four questions were asked in five- Point-Likert formats regarding the use of SMS among the respondents.

1. I often use mobile SMS when I communicate with others.
2. I often read SMS messages received on my mobile phone.
3. I am familiar with using SMS on a mobile phone.
4. I can operate the mobile phone on its own

Johan *et al*; discovered in 2007 that the success of e-government service delivery using SMS could be increased if citizens could use SMS. Accordingly, the responses given by the respondents to examine the Use of SMS by applicants who come to make their Identity cards from One day service are reported in table 6.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents by the use of SMS

Factor	%				
	strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	strongly disagree
Often use mobile SMSs	18	40	23	16	3
Often read SMS	19	40	21	17	5
Familiar with using SMS	23	38	19	17	4
Ability to operate the mobile phone on its own	7	38	35	13	7

In asking the response to all 04 questions of the above Likert model, it was discovered that more than 75% of the respondents communicate using short messages. Accordingly, this study has shown the usage of SMS service provided by DRP as an m-government service and the Use of SMS by individuals have positively correlated. The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship between ($r=0.472$, $p= 0.000$) in usage of SMS service and use of SMS service of DRP.

Accordingly, it has appeared that when the use of SMS increases, the usage of SMS services of DRP also increases. Since the use of short messages has decreased to some extent with the development of technology, the relatively new generation has moved away from using text messages and is tempted to use social media such as WhatsApp and Viber. Hence, using short messages as an m-government service is now an outdated method (Rogers, 2003). It has been revealed in the study based on e-government methods in America, but Sri Lanka is an Asian country, and the m- government concept is also a new concept to Sri Lanka. In that case, the relationship between the use of SMS and mobile phones and SMS usage of DRP as an m- government service was studied.

As the use of technology increases, user satisfaction also increases, so government policymakers should create e-government systems that match the needs, desires, and

expectations of citizens (Alawneh and Batiha, 2013). However, this study also found that increased use of technology or texting increases customer satisfaction. The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship between technological factors and SMS usage frequency ($r=0.478$, $p=0.000$). The use of technology/ use of SMS, increasing gradually means an increase in user satisfaction.

4.4. Dependent Variable Analysis

Two dependent variables were mainly considered in this study. They were usage of SMS Service of the DRP and User Satisfaction. Focusing on those variables, the study of correlation and effect between the independent and dependent variables was done.

4.4.1. SMS usage of DRP as an m- governance service.

The usage of SMS service provided by the Department for Registration of Persons as an m-governance service was studied here. A question was included in the questionnaire to ask about the usage of SMS service introduced by the DRP.

1. Were you tempted to see the SMS delivered by DRP? And 03 answers were given to that, Yes, No, and Don't know.

It was revealed that 125 respondents used SMS. Out of a sample of 150, 25 respondents did not use SMS of DRP. 19 respondents did not know whether the SMS was received on their phones. But 06 have received and were not open. Accordingly, the responses were used to inquire how effective DRP has provided this short message service as an m-government service.

Internal, external, and technological factors were studied as independent variables for the usage of SMS service. In similar research conducted by Chien *et al*; in 2017, individual differences, Technology Differences, and Demographics have been used to study the correlation and impact of the usage of text messages. But in the study done by Muk and Chung in 2014, the correlation and influence were studied using Perceived ease of use of

SMS (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness of SMS (PU), Social Influence of (SI), and Attitudes toward Acceptance of SMS (ATA).

The responses given by the 25 people who did not use the SMS service provided by DRP are shown in Table.4, out of which most of them i.e. (n=6) 21% of respondents were not tempted to use this service provided by the government considering that it is not useful. (n=6) 21% were unable to use the service as they did not have mobile phones. (n=5) 17% of respondents did not use the SMS service provided by DRP because they did not know how to use SMS and could not read English SMS. (n=4) 14% of respondents have refused to use the SMS service provided by DRP apart from technical glitches of (n=3) 10% due to a lack of trust in such technical services. The Trust of citizens is an important factor influencing the success of e-government projects. Governments should build trustworthy relationships using good awareness with citizens before attempting to open such e-channels with them (Zeleti, 2011; Warkentin *et al*; 2002).

By studying the internal factors, external factors, and technical factors that affect the usage of SMS service provided by DRP, it has been concluded that there is more inclination to use SMS service in DRP. This study also studied the association between user satisfactions with the use of SMS services. The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship between usage of SMS and user satisfaction ($r=0.478$, $p=0.000$). It revealed when the use of SMS service provided by DRP increases, the satisfaction of SMS service users also increases, and when the satisfaction increases, the use of SMS also increases. In 2009, Keoduangsin and Goodwin revealed 2010, that user experience, user characteristics, and user satisfaction depend on the use of mobile services.

4.4.2. User Satisfaction

Depending on the success and failure of a text messaging service, users will have more or less satisfied with the service (Park, 2008). Several independent factors also were considered to measure the satisfaction of the SMS service introduced by DRP as an m-government

service. Today, citizens have lots of choices on where and who to deal with. As a result, the power has now shifted to the citizens. If they feel such government service is not satisfying their expectations, they will simply reject them (Bonits *et al.*, 2007). The extent to which the DRP-directed text messaging service has resulted in respondent satisfaction was assessed using the five-point Likert model.

"I am satisfied with the provision of such a technical service by the DRP." Figure 07, has shown the responses given by the respondents.

User satisfaction

Figure 7: Distribution of respondents of DRP by the level of satisfaction with the SMS service

In using this SMS service introduced by DRP, 26% respondents have strongly agreed and 36% have agreed. 19% were neutral but 17% were disagreed and 2 % strongly disagreed. Accordingly, it has been found that less than 20% of the respondents did not agree and strongly disagreed with the SMS service provided by DRP.

In the inquiry about the 29 respondents who were not satisfied with the DRP SMS, it was revealed that apart from the 25 respondents who did not receive the SMS, there were also 04 people who received the SMS of DRP.

- As indicated by the two respondents, (13th) and (80th), they couldn't be satisfied with such services because they have no experience and lack the confidence to use m-governance services.

- The 110th respondent received the SMS, after obtaining the National Identity Card.
- The 67th respondent waited for almost 04 hours and inquired. The staff has informed him that the process of the national identity card has been delayed due to an incomplete application. Therefore, it was informed that it is not appropriate to wait for the text message to be received.

However, more than 75% of the people were at least moderately satisfied with the SMS service provided by DRP. Mobile technology is the easiest way to improve people-to-people connections and access services. Accordingly, in the provision of services by the government using mobile technology, the service's popularity will increase if the people receiving those services are oriented toward the technology (Keoduangsin and Goodwin, 2009)

Trust and satisfaction in any service are built on its' usefulness. Citizens are generally reluctant to depend on certain services provided by the government. But if the service is useful for them, the temptation to use it can also be seen (Hubaishi and Ahmad, 2018). SMS can be introduced as an effective communication option that helps users in communication, and service utility. The satisfaction of the respondents also varies (Davis et al; 1989). Accordingly, to study the respondents' satisfaction with using the SMS service provided by DRP, the ease of use and usefulness of the SMS service were studied.

4.4.2.1. Ease of use

As introduced by Davis and Warshaw in 1989, the Ease of Use (PEU) of a product or service is the extent to which a person believes that the service will be easy to understand and use. Recently and Heijden, (2004) reported that perceived ease of use (PEU) has both direct and indirect impacts through perceived usefulness (PU). In this study ease of use of SMS service was measured to examine the satisfaction of using the SMS service provided by DRP. For that, questions were asked in the five-point Likert format.

“This service is quite easy to use as the message is delivered as a text message”

Accordingly, in this study, under the m-governance concept, the relationship between the Ease of Use of SMS and the usage of SMS service provided by DRP has been examined. It has been revealed that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship between ease of use of SMS technology and the usage of SMS service of DRP($r=0.649$, $p=0.000$). Accordingly, it was studied, when the ease of using the text message service increases, SMS usage also increases.

In this study, to ask how easy the text message service provided by DRP is, a Likert-type statement was directly asked, "This Service was easy to use as the message is delivered as a text message." The response is shown in figure 08, in which ($n=57$) 38% of the respondents strongly agreed that this service is easy to use. Furthermore, ($n=50$) 32% of the respondents agreed, and ($n=14$) 9% gave a neutral response. But ($n=26+3$) 19% of respondents strongly disagreed, stating that SMS service is not easy to use. Accordingly, it was inferred that the majority of people could use the SMS service of DRP easily.

Figure 8: Distribution of respondents of DRP by the level of ease of use of the SMS service

On the other hand, it was hypothesized that if the m-government service provided by DRP is successful and easy to use, the satisfaction of the service beneficiaries will also increase. Accordingly, it was investigated whether there is an interrelationship between client satisfaction and ease of using the SMS service.

The results indicated that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship ($r=0.660$, $p=0.000$) between in user satisfaction and ease of use of SMS in DRP. Here, it was revealed that as the ease of use of the SMS service introduced by the DRP increases, the satisfaction of the service users increases. Thus it was revealed that the SMS service provided by the Department for Registration of persons is easy to use for the people who are useful to it.

4.4.2.2. Usefulness

Accordingly, this study investigated to what extent its use affects user satisfaction for the Short message service introduced by DRP as an m-government service. To increase the applicant's satisfaction, the DRP sends a text message to the applicants who come to get the service through the one-day service. Once the National ID card is prepared, an SMS will be sent informing about it to increase the applicant's satisfaction. This service helps to avoid standing in queues until the National ID card is processed, to come and receive the ID card at the right time, and to manage their time or do any other needs until the National ID card is processed. Venkatesh and Davis 2000 revealed that individuals are motivated to adopt or use a technology if it is adequate to fulfill their needs and usefulness.

It takes 03 hours for the DRP to prepare a National Identity Card, during which time they may leave the department premises for other purposes. It is also possible to manage time using the text message received after the National ID card is prepared. It is also possible to come at the proper time and collect the National Identity Card without having to stand in queues. Accordingly, two five-point Likert-type questions were asked to examine the extent to which the SMS service was useful to the applicants coming to prepare their National ID cards.

1. This service is very useful as it enables me to manage my time effectively on that day.
2. This service was helpful for me as it notified me when to collect the ID.

According to the responses given to these questions, the extent to which the SMS service of DRP has been easy to use has been investigated. As identified in 2009 by Kargin et al; in order to the usage of a mobile service, its perceived usefulness must be high. Accordingly, it was revealed that there was a positive significant ($\alpha=0.01$) relationship ($r=0.618$, $p= 0.000$) between the usefulness of the DRP SMS service and user satisfaction. The primary objective of this study was to develop the applicants' satisfaction with the SMS service of DRP. Accordingly, it was discovered that when the usefulness of the SMS service provided by DRP increases, the satisfaction of the users also increases.

The responses are given regarding the use of SMS service to manage time. 42% of people who used the text message sent by the DRP strongly agree with that statement and they could manage their time. Not only that, 30% agreed, and 07% were neutral. But 19% of respondents disagreed and 01% strongly disagreed with this statement. There 41% of people who have strongly agreed with the statement that they were able to collect their ID cards on time from the counters. Furthermore, 33% have agreed, and 05% have become neutral. But 18% disagreed and 03% strongly disagreed with this statement. But relatively, the number of people who have used the SMS service is much higher than those who have not. According to the 21% of the respondents, the majority stated that they were inconvenienced because the counter number was not recorded in the SMS even though they received the SMS to get the ID card. Those responses were shown in the figure.09 below.

Figure 9: Distribution of respondents by the level of usefulness of the SMS service

From the above information, it was revealed that the SMS service introduced by DRP is relatively useful and has achieved effective results.

4.5. Findings

- The results of this research show that males are more inclined than females to use the SMS service introduced by DRP. It was revealed that men are more inclined to use such technical services provided by the concept of m-governance compared to women.
- Inquiring whether age affects the use of the SMS service introduced by DRP, it was revealed that DRP was offered as an m-governance service by people under 30 years of age, i.e. between 15 and 30 years of age compared to people above 30 years of age. Showed a greater tendency to use text messages.
- In the study of the factors influencing the usage of SMS service introduced by DRP, it was revealed that the level of education of a person is a factor. That is, it was discovered that people with good education levels are more inclined to use these m-governance services.
- The short message service, introduced by DRP, is sent in English only. People with English literacy can understand text messages, but people with low English literacy have less ability to understand the message. In this study, it was discovered that as English literacy increased, the usage of text messaging also increased.
- Level of awareness is a very important factor to develop the usage of short messaging services. This study revealed that people are motivated to use new services if they have proper awareness. Using the sample of 150 users and non-users of the SMS service, it was revealed that most of the people became aware of the DRP's SMS

service after coming to the department to avail of the service. Therefore, the use of this text message could have been increased if awareness was given at the time of filling out the National ID card application.

- Considering the relationship between the living areas of the respondents and the usage of the SMS service provided by the DRP, it has been found that people living in urban or suburban have a greater tendency to use such short m-governance services.
- Moreover, due to the ability to use technology and the ability to use text messages, the usage of the text message service introduced by the Department for Registration of Persons has increased. It was found that the satisfaction of respondents using the short messages provided by DRP as an m-governance service has increased significantly, and this has been attributed to the ease of use and usefulness of the SMS service.

4.6. Perceived Problems of the SMS service of DRP as an M- government Service

- The SMS service introduced by the Department for Registration of Persons was expected to increase the satisfaction of the clients and the expected results were found to be successful. But some problems were also identified which affect the success of this SMS service.
- The fact that SMS service is provided only in English is a problem for people with language difficulties.
- Due to lack of awareness at the time of filling the applications regarding the text message service, some of the service beneficiaries may mention non-working phone

numbers mention the phone numbers of other people do not mention the phone number or mark the wrong phone numbers. Because of this, due to the difficulty of making proper communication, the desired result of the text message service has not been given.

- Due to the lack of reliability of the users regarding these m-governance and e-governance services provided by the government, they were reluctant to use such services, so they stayed for almost 03 hours in the service premises and did not use the SMS service of DRP.
- In the case of using technical services such as text messaging services, persons with limited technical abilities are not able to use text messaging services. Therefore, it was discovered that there are people who are not interested in this m-government service.
- Due to the limitation of 25 characters used in the short message service provided by DRP, the information contained therein may not provide the correct guidance to the users. It was recognized that users are facing some inconvenience as the SMS mentions that the applicant's National ID card has been processed but does not specify which counter the person should go to.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the effectiveness of the SMS service introduced by DRP, and the results of the study revealed the effectiveness of the SMS service as an m-government initiative. The study revealed the problems, and conclusions and recommendations were given based on the information.

5.1. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, text message service was identified as the primary service provided by individuals using their mobile communication devices. Regardless of age, education level, and region of residence, the person can use SMS services. Communication through SMS is increasing daily and can be widely used for personal, business, and messaging purposes; thus, there is potential to provide mobile government services.

The primary objective of introducing m-governance services or e-governance services to DRP is to increase customer satisfaction. Text messaging services can be a primary mobile technology method for providing services efficiently to individuals. Government-to-citizen services can be provided based on building effective communication with the public. This study concludes that government should give easy-to-use and helpful m-governance services to improve usage and client satisfaction.

It was discovered that when the government introduces new services, customers must be aware. The main challenges in providing m-government services are the public's lack of trust in government services. Therefore, in delivering m-government services, it is appropriate for organizations to provide services reliably with proper awareness. When providing government-to-citizen services under m-governance, the effectiveness of the service can be increased by using familiar technology for the majority of the public. Text messaging is a

technology service that can be used by people of any education level living in any area. Moreover, simple technical devices should be used to provide services to the general public.

5.2. Recommendations

- Providing SMS service of DRP only in the English language is a problem to understand for those with language difficulties. It is recommended that the service be more effective if it is provided as a trilingual service depending on the user's language preference.
- An additional phone call or a voice recording needs to be arranged to notify that the National ID card has been prepared.
- It is necessary to inform the applicants when filling out the application about the SMS service provided by the DRP can avoid problems in sending the SMS to the applicants.
- At least 03 SMSs should be sent till the process is completed and clients can understand the status of their National ID card process. Also, if there are any defective documents, they can obtain the National Identity Card on time by correcting them.

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